

Leveraging Data Plane Acceleration For Network Coding Deployment: A Measurement Study

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Abstract—This paper focuses on integrating Data Plane Development Kit (DPDK) and Service Function Chaining (SFC) on the OpenStack cloud OS to support network coding, enabling the OpenStack instance to function as a virtualized network coding service. The main points are: comparing OpenvSwitch-DPDK with native OpenvSwitch to confirm DPDK’s significant network throughput improvement, using SFC to arrange packet processing sequences of instances for varying network coding functionalities, and combining OpenvSwitch and the kernel inside each instance to enable network coding. Performance evaluation and results analysis are presented, demonstrating the feasibility of network coding as a service on any virtual machine with a commodity CPU. Future work includes advancing network coding function virtualization with more automation and intelligence.

Index Terms—Network Function Virtualization, Network Coding, OpenStack

I. INTRODUCTION

Network Function Virtualization (NFV) revolutionizes the cloud and telecommunication industry, decoupling software functionalities from physical hardware to enhance flexibility using commodity hardware and virtualization technologies for network functions (NF) [1]. While NFV offers flexibility, high reliability is crucial in modern networks [2]. Network coding (NC), specifically Random Linear Network Coding (RLNC) [3], is an advanced technology that increases communication system reliability and capacity. NC intelligently combines packets using encoder and recorded functions, adding redundancy where needed and improving network performance with higher throughput, reliability, and resilience against packet loss or failures [4].

Deploying NC functions (*e.g.*, encoder and decoder) as virtual network functions (vNF) offers flexibility, allowing dynamic allocation of distributed NC functions closer to users [5]. However, critical challenges exist. NC requires complex deployment, distributed over the network with various parameters, necessitating network automation [6]. Another challenge is chaining NC functions without relying on underlying network infrastructures, as improper chaining reduces efficiency and can lead to lost packets [5]. Network agility is required to address this challenge. Additionally, virtualizing NC introduces significant latency overhead, making real-time communication challenging for latency-sensitive applications

like the Tactile Internet. Most previous research on implementing NC as a service has primarily focused on proposing architectures or prototypes that only support subsets of the NC components [7], [8]. These studies have been mostly limited to simulation environments or small-scale and simple testbeds, resulting in limited scalability and applicability in real-world environments [9]–[11]. Moreover, these studies have not addressed network automation and network agility in their proposal for NC as a service.

We aim to support network automation, network agility, and low latency for NC in cloud computing. To support network automation for NC, we facilitate the deployment of NC functions by adopting an automated deployment process that uses binary files to generate NC libraries, thus eliminating the code compilation step, which is time-consuming and error-prone. To support network agility for NC, we utilized Service Function Chaining (SFC) [12] to allow the dynamic chaining of NC functions and steer the traffic between them, independent of the underlying network infrastructures. We employ a packet processing acceleration technique (DPDK) that bypasses the Linux kernel and passes the packets directly to the user plane to reduce the latency introduced by virtualized NC functions. Our implementation results indicate the feasibility of deploying NC as NFV in real-world scenarios, encompassing widely adopted virtualization platforms. The performance of this deployment was notably enhanced by incorporating DPDK, resulting in improved throughput up to 8 times and a 14% reduction in packet loss.

II. RELATED WORK

Random linear network coding (RLNC) [3] is a Forward Error Correction family of code, providing a nearly optimal and distributed approach to create linear combinations using random coefficients (or coding vectors) at network nodes. RLNC source and intermediate nodes conduct random linear combinations on input data to generate output data. These combinations are independently executed at each node, and then the node sends the coding vector along with the output data to the next hops. In other words, each node i) performs a random linear combination on the input data, ii) updates the coding vector of the input data, and iii) sends the updated

coding vector together with the output data [13], [14]. These coding vectors allow intermediate nodes to re-create new coded packets and send them to destinations. The destination recovers the original packets using the received coding vectors.

NC as a service: Various studies have proposed different architectures and prototypes to leverage network coding for improving data transport performance in diverse virtualization environments. Some of these prototypes and architectures aim to integrate network coding into the SDN environment. In [10], the authors deployed RLNC within Mininet [15] virtual containers to execute network coding functions, while the SDN controller managed traffic flow. Similarly, the researchers in [11] capitalized on the benefits of softwarization and programmability offered by 5G communication networks. They deployed RLNC as VNF to reduce packet loss in the core network. Their approach involved utilizing OpenFlow-compatible SDN switches and three physical hosts for deploying the network coding function as VNF. While the prototypes proposed in [9]–[11] were relatively simple and employed emulators or small-scale testbeds, researchers in [7] took a step further, and deployed network coding as VNF in a real cloud environment with geo-distributed cloud data centers. Additionally, they proposed efficient algorithms for dynamically deploying and scaling network coding functions based on demand, considering user locations. The results demonstrated improved throughput and enhanced robustness, particularly in multicast sessions.

Acceleration techniques: The primary obstacle in utilizing network coding as a service or VNF is the network input/output (I/O) process, which involves packet processing in the Linux kernel and copying packets between kernel space and user space, leading to decreased performance [16], [17]. However, various techniques have been proposed to achieve high-performance packet processing in virtual and software environments. These techniques include bypassing the Linux Kernel using methods like DPDK and netmap [18], as well as in-kernel processing through tools like extended Berkeley Packet Filter (eBPF) and the eXpress Data Path (XDP) [19]. Due to its operation in user space, DPDK offers greater flexibility and can be utilized in a broader range of use cases. Several studies, such as [20], [21], have explored the use of DPDK in various environments and cloud platforms. DPDK’s ease of integration has made it widely supported by popular cloud platforms such as Docker, Kubernetes, and OpenStack. XDP is examined by many studies, with Vieira et al. [22] discussing its potentials, while [23], [24] address some of its limitations primarily arising from the use of eBPF. These limitations include a restricted program size, limited support for loops, and inadequate support for sending the same packet on multiple ports (e.g., multicast or flooding). As a result, XDP is more suitable for specific and simple network functions rather than complex and general packet processing tasks, including network coding. Some studies tried to use both Linux kernel bypassing and in-kernel processing. Xiang et al. [8] proposed a combination of kernel bypassing and in-kernel processing acceleration methods. They introduced a

Fig. 1: SFC Network in between Compute nodes.

method for classifying VNFs based on their complexity, which helps determine whether to run the function in user space using DPDK or in the Linux kernel using XDP. To examine their proposed method, they used an NC (encoder only) as a VNF, considering network coding as an advanced network function that should run in user space.

However, many of the previous works attempted to implement network coding as a service. None of them have fully integrated the entire network coding chain (encoder, recoder, and decoder) along with packet processing acceleration technologies. Additionally, the performance improvements achieved through acceleration techniques and the impact of using SFC to regulate traffic paths have rarely been considered, particularly in real-world deployments and within widely used virtualization platforms.

III. MEASUREMENT TECHNOLOGY

Our goal is to provide an empirical measurement study of NC in cloud computing using packet processing acceleration and SFC. Toward this goal, we start with how to deploy NC functions in cloud computing. Since NC functions in cloud computing incur the overheads (e.g., latency) from virtualization, we then present our approach to leveraging DPDK to accelerate the processing of NC functions. Afterward, to perform NC operation in cloud computing, we describe how to use SFC to chain NC functions including encoder, recoder, and decoder.

A. The Deployment of NC

Considering the great potential of NC, we propose to implement NC in cloud computing. Among existing cloud computing platforms, we adopt OpenStack which is a carrier-grade cloud computing platform. Specifically, we use OpenStack Nova component to deploy NC functions (i.e., encoder, recoder, and decoder) on virtual machines (VMs). Specifically, to avoid the time-consuming and error-prone compiling process of NC, we first use binary files (.deb files) to rapidly generate executable NC libraries (.so files). Afterwards, we have to allow NC functions to act as a network function, i.e., receiving packets from an ingress interface, handling them, and sending them out through an egress interface. Toward this aim, we could simply modify existing NC source code to

support forwarding functionality to dispatch packets. However, adding this forwarding feature could hinder the flexibility of NC as we have to specify interfaces to dispatch packets. Moreover, this support introduces development efforts, thus making it inadequate for the large-scale deployment of NC in OpenStack, *i.e.*, to deploy an NC function on a specific VM, we have to change the source code to specify ingress and egress interfaces. Consequently, we first use NCNet [11] to create an NC interface, which is a virtual interface for the processing of each NC function, *i.e.*, by invoking NC binaries. For instance, an NC function for the encoder receives packets, encodes them, and then sends them out. On each VM, we then install Open vSwitch (OVS) [25], a popular software switch, to connect the NC interface with other VM interfaces (*e.g.*, ingress and egress interfaces). Consequently, OVS receives packets from the ingress interface, forwards them to the NC interface, and sends them out through the egress interface.

B. Acceleration

We proceed to improve the processing performance of NC functions on VMs. Traditionally, a Network Interface Card (NIC) first receives packets, transfers them to the Linux kernel network stack (*i.e.*, for Kernel processing such as routing), and then forwards them to VMs for further processing. Various acceleration technologies such as DPDK and XDP have been proposed to reduce the overheads (*e.g.*, latency) of Linux kernel network stack. DPDK bypasses the Linux kernel stack, thus transferring packets directly from NIC to user space. Meanwhile, XDP still relies on in-kernel processing but allows packets to be processed before traversing through the Linux kernel network stack. However, DPDK has been demonstrated to outperform XDP (*e.g.*, in terms of throughput [26]) as DPDK completely bypasses kernel processing. Moreover, from the implementation perspective, XDP has been maintained in the Linux kernel source code [19]. Therefore, using XDP requires a specific Linux kernel release and consequently introduces maintenance effort, *i.e.*, updating new XDP features ends up updating a new Linux kernel release. Considering this issue, OpenStack widely adopts DPDK to accelerate the performance of VMs. Note that as mentioned in Section III-A we installed OVS inside the VM to support NC. Meanwhile, OpenStack also uses OVS as a networking plugin to provide networking between VMs.

We proceed to present how to apply DPDK to each VM that runs an NC function in OpenStack. DPDK support in OpenStack is realized through using networking-ovs-dpdk [27] that integrates OVS-DPDK [28] into OpenStack. OVS is adopted as a default networking plugin in OpenStack. However, since OVS implements its datapath in the kernel space, OVS-DPDK has been designed to integrate DPDK in OVS, thus allowing the OVS datapath implemented in the user space. Consequently, networking-ovs-dpdk brings the support of OVS-DPDK to OpenStack. For each VM that runs an NC function, DPDK assigns a *virtio* interface to the VM that is paired with a *Vhost* interface in OVS-DPDK.

C. Service Function Chaining

To perform the NC operation, we have to chain NC functions. Specifically, an encoder first encodes original packets to generate encoded packets that are then forwarded to a recoder. When the recoder receives the encoded packets, it decodes them to increase the chance to recover the original packets at the destination in terms of packet loss. Afterwards, when receiving the recoded packets from the recoder, a decoder then decodes them to get the original packets. To deploy such chained NC functions in OpenStack, we use OpenStack networking-SFC [29] that implements SFC for steering traffic between VMs with a specific order. The procedure of creating an SFC in OpenStack is performed as follows. First, networking-SFC creates a flow classifier (an OVS bridge) based on predefined matching fields (*e.g.*, source and destination IP addresses) to differentiate incoming flows. In OpenStack, Neutron (an OpenStack networking service) associates logical ports (*i.e.*, ingress port and egress port) with VM interfaces (*i.e.*, ingress and egress interfaces). Afterwards, networking-SFC creates a port pair including the ingress port and egress port of each VM. Since multiple VMs can run the same network function, networking-SFC then creates a port-pair group that includes the port pairs of these VMs. Next, networking-SFC creates a port chain consisting of the flow classifier and port pair groups. Finally, networking-SFC populates the port chain configuration to OVS in OpenStack. Since we use OVS-DPDK to accelerate the performance of the chained NC functions, the only difference is that the logical port for each VM indicates the logical connection between the *virtio* interface of the VM and the *vHost* interface of the OVS-DPDK.

IV. MEASUREMENT SETUP

In this section, we will explain the setup for the experiments by describing the testbed setting, the software used, and the deployment process.

A. Testbed

Our testbed consists of four physical machines and two separate Gigabit Ethernet networks. One of the physical machines, referred to as *controller node*, is used for managing the platform, while the other three machines, referred to as *compute nodes*, are used for processing and storage. The two separate networks provided by the testbed are used as follows: *i*) a control network for the control traffic between the controller node and the compute nodes, and *ii*) a data network for the data traffic traversed between the compute nodes. This network setting has been widely used in cloud platforms such as OpenStack to eliminate the mutual impact between the control and data traffic, thus allowing us to obtain reliable results.

The controller node has 16GB RAM and two DPDK-compatible Intel I217-LM network cards. The other three worker nodes have 4GB RAM and two Intel I219-V network cards each. All four machines run Ubuntu 16.04 LTS as their operating system.

(a) Practical receiving data rate on different sending data rates

(b) Receiving data rate on different packet size

Fig. 2: Comparison of UDP throughput performance with different sending rates and packet sizes.

B. Software Components

We set up an OpenStack Cloud Platform that simulates the real-world deployment [30] which includes one controller and three compute nodes. OpenStack (Pike release) is used on all nodes. We deployed two major OpenStack services including Nova and Neutron on the controller node. Specifically, OpenStack Nova service is responsible for controlling the provision of compute instances (*e.g.*, VMs) on the compute nodes. Meanwhile, OpenStack Neutron service accounts for providing network services (*e.g.*, IP addresses) for compute instances. On each compute node, we deployed agents to support the OpenStack services on the controller node. Specifically, Nova service on the controller node invokes Nova agent on a target compute node to provision a VM.

OpenStack supports many hypervisors [31], we adapted the open-source QEMU hypervisor (version 2.5.0) for this work, as it offers helpful tools for debugging and development. All VMs in this OpenStack platform uses xenial server cloud image as the boot image and come with 1 vCPU, 1 GB RAM, and 10 GB storage.

Unlike default OpenStack network support that only requires an OVS agent on each network node, Networking-DPDK relies on OVS-DPDK agent, *i.e.*, the integration of DPDK in OVS. We adopted common DPDK (release 17.05) settings on each compute node. Moreover, in our evaluation, network coding functions including encoder, and decoder are deployed on the compute nodes that form a service function chain as shown in Fig. 1. Subsequently, we deployed OpenStack Networking-SFC, which is the extension of Neutron service to steer data traffic through the chain of the network coding functions.

DPDK uses hugepages to improve performance and optimize memory management in high-speed packet processing applications. In this work, we created 1024 hugepages, whereby each hugepage size is set to 2 MB.

To generate the traffic needed for the evaluations, we used the free and open-source package **iperf** [32]. iperf is widely

Fig. 3: Comparison of UDP packet loss between different scenarios.

used in research and industry to do network measurements. It can tune timing, buffers, and protocols (TCP, UDP) and reports bandwidth, loss, and other parameters.

C. Deployment Procedure

The deployment process of OpenStack DPDK platform is complex due to the number of components and the high dependencies between them. To make the deployment easier to reproduce and repeat, we divided the process into three tiers: *i*) OpenStack DPDK, *ii*) SFC, and *iii*) Network coding virtualization. For the OpenStack DPDK tier, we used *Devstack* [33], a tool provided by OpenStack that helps to quickly install and set up the platform. *Devstack* comes with a plugin called *networking-ovs-dpdk* that configures all hosts to utilize DPDK-accelerated OVS instead of unaccelerated OVS, this will accelerate the overall packet processing performance in the platform.

In the second tier, we deployed one VM on each compute node. To implement SFC in Neutron, we used *networking-sfc* plugin [29] to configure the traffic flow between the deployed VMs. SFC is essential to ensure the traffic follows a specific path needed in the network coding scenarios between VMs.

The third tier of the deployment process is to deploy NC-as-service. In each VM, we first installed *NCNet* [11] and OVS (version 2.8.2). OVS bridge interface is configured to

have the same MAC address that is assigned to the VM by OpenStack Neutron to maintain the connection with the OpenStack platform. In each VM, a new virtual interface is created using *NCNet*, the type of the interface depends on the NC functionality the VM will provide (e.g., the VM that works as an encoder will have a virtual interface of type encoder).

V. EVALUATION RESULTS

Our primary objective is to assess the effectiveness of our proposed approach in addressing the challenges associated with implementing NC-as-Service. We begin by evaluating the performance advantages of adopting OVS-DPDK compared to Native OVS, aiming to ascertain its capability to enhance the overall performance of NC. Subsequently, we evaluate employing SFC to dynamically chain NC functions and its impact on the performance of NC.

A. Comparison of OVS-DPDK with Native OVS

Our goal in this part of the experiment is to determine how much performance improvement can be achieved by using DPDK with OVS-DPDK instead of native OVS in OpenStack. We investigated the performance of OVS with the support of DPDK in OpenStack in terms of throughput and packet loss for UDP traffic in three different scenarios:

- 1) **Pure-DPDK:** Both VMs are using OVS-DPDK.
- 2) **Hybrid:** One VM is using OVS-DPDK, while the other VM is using the native OVS.
- 3) **Baseline:** Both VMs are using native OVS.

To investigate the effect of DPDK on the throughput and packet loss of UDP, we considered two variable factors: *i*) Sending data rate and *ii*) Packet size. For the sending data rate factor, we used a fixed packet size of 1472 Bytes. Fig. 2a shows that using OVS-DPDK improved the throughput performance 8 times more than native OVS. We also observe from Fig. 2a that when using OVS-DPDK on one or both VMs the throughput grows as the sending data rate increases and reached nearly 820 Mbit/s. Meanwhile, using native OVS on both VMs, the throughput stopped increasing at sending data rate of 200 Mbit/s. Fig. 2a also indicates that there is a minimal disparity in throughput between OVS and OVS-DPDK at lower sending rates (below 200 Mbit/s). This obtained result demonstrates that OVS-DPDK is better suited for higher data rates, particularly when employing sending rates exceeding 200 Mbit/s.

To examine the impact of the packet size factor, we fixed the sending data rate at 800 Mbit/s. In Fig. 2b, the result shows that the Pure-DPDK scenario achieves much higher throughput than the Baseline scenario. Specifically, Pure-DPDK reached nearly 820 Mbit/s when the packet size is around 1400 Bytes which is 7 times the Baseline scenario at the same packet size. The UDP results for both variables show that, unlike native OVS, utilizing OVS-DPDK significantly enhances the throughput performance, particularly when employing higher sending rates and larger packet sizes.

The packet loss comparison between OVS-DPDK and native OVS is shown in Fig. 3. The results show that the packet loss

Fig. 4: Comparison of virtualized network coding performance with/without SFC

Fig. 5: Comparison of virtualized network coding packet loss with/without SFC

reduced from 16% when using native OVS to less than 2% when using OVS-DPDK in both VMs. The high packet loss observed when using native OVS can be caused by packet drops, especially with high data rates. This situation arises because native OVS may not be able to process all incoming packets quickly enough, leading to situations where the UDP buffer becomes full and packet drop occurs.

In summary, the results approved our assumptions that using DPDK as a software acceleration technique will improve the overall throughput performance of the network and reduce the packet loss in UDP mode significantly, which makes it ideal to be used in cloud infrastructures that need to support virtualized services and functions.

B. Virtualized Network Coding Performance in OpenStack DPDK Cloud Platform

We proceed to investigate the advantages of adapting SFC in our approach and examine the impact of SFC on the performance of NC deployed in OpenStack in terms of throughput and packet loss. All VMs in this experiment use DPDK-OVS (Pure-DPDK).

Fig. 4 plots the comparison of virtualized NC performance with and without SFC. The results show that using SFC to steer the data traffic between the VMs reduced the throughput performance by 80% in comparison with using direct connections between VMs. Additionally, the graph shows that

increasing the packet size does not make much difference in the throughput when SFC is enabled in comparison with the obvious effect of the packet size when using direct connections between VMs. SFC also introduces 5% more packet loss as shown in Fig. 5. Our investigation of SFC reveals that SFC can introduce latency and lower the network throughput by adding extra processing load to the network. Moreover, in our scenario, using OVS within the VM to connect to NCNet can also be a limiting factor. Further research is required to investigate methods that can improve the performance of SFC in cloud environments such as OpenStack.

Despite the overhead that arises from using SFC, it offers significant advantages in terms of flexibility and ease of deployment for our virtualized NC implementation. This makes it a viable and valuable choice to adapt, enabling us to overcome the complex requirements to deploy the NC effectively and support the network agility.

VI. CONCLUSION

Virtualizing network coding offers opportunities for improved network performance in terms of reliability and flexibility, but it also brings critical challenges like network automation, network agility, and latency. In this paper, we proposed an approach for supporting low latency, network automation, and network agility in cloud computing for virtualized NC. We used DPDK to bypass the Linux kernel to reduce latency and directly pass packets to the user plane. We employed binary files for network automation to generate NC functions instead of time-consuming code compilation. To achieve network agility, we utilized SFC for dynamic chaining of NC functions and traffic steering, independent of underlying network infrastructures. We evaluated our approach's effectiveness by comparing OVS-DPDK with Native OVS to assess its capability to enhance NC performance. We examined the impact of employing SFC to dynamically chain NC functions. The study shows that DPDK significantly improves throughput and reduces packet loss. However, introducing SFC in network coding deployment may introduce some overhead. These findings highlight the benefits of leveraging DPDK for improved performance and the trade-offs associated with SFC in network coding within OpenStack.

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